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Soviet Boarding School: Throw away And Forget Or Take the Best

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Abstract

The actuality of the problem raised in the article is due to the fact that at present social support for orphans is one of the key tasks of the country. The issue of preparing children from boarding schools for life in a rapidly changing society is quite urgent. In the current century, in the course of the pedagogical process in special boarding schools, orphans and children left without parental care develop their personality and prepare them for further independent life. In carrying out this training, the pedagogical teams actively return to the heritage of outstanding teachers of the past. Proceeding from this, the demand for creative, substantial and methodical potential of the soviet upbringing; the analysis of theoretical developments and applied methods of the socialization process of the child are of great importance.

The aim of the study is to present in a holistic form, based on the materials of residential institutions for orphans in the late XX - early XXI century in the context of the ideas of Kondratenkov (1921-1992), the practical implementation of the process of preparing orphans and children left without parental care to independent life in society.

The leading method in the study of this problem was the historical and pedagogical method, which allowed to identify the key ideas of one of the founders of the boarding school pedagogy Kondratenkov.

In the article the authors revealed the main ideas of Kondratenkov, used by teaching staff in boarding schools in the late XX - early XXI century by the organization of educational work with orphans. The authors also revealed the main methods, forms and means of education of orphans in boarding schools in the late XX - early XXI century.

The materials presented in the article can be used in the development of teaching-methodical complexes, reading of lectures and special courses on pedagogy, history of pedagogy, writing of theses for course works and diploma works on the above topics.

Keywords: boarding schools, educational work, orphans, Kondratenkov, labour, family education.

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Introduction

The urgency of the problem raised in the article is due to the fact that in modern Russia, social support for orphans is one of the key tasks of the country. Today the question of preparing children from boarding schools for life in a rapidly changing society is quite important. To solve this problem, programs have been developed to reduce orphanhood and provide children with a home. One of such programs is the Government Programme “Assistance to Orphans in Russia”, enacted on August 1, 2018. It involves developing the activities of public associations and groups at the local level that contribute to improving the situation of orphans and changing society’s attitude towards them, supporting initiatives aimed at exchanging information and strengthening cooperation between various organizations and institutions working with children. In addition to Government programmes, several special programmes were developed, such as a “Concept for the development of the system for the prevention of child neglect and juvenile delinquency for the period from 2017 to 2020” (2017) and the Federal Target Programme “Russia without orphans” for years 2013-2020 (2012). “Concept for the development of the system for the prevention of child neglect and juvenile delinquency for the period from 2017 to 2020” (2017) assumes creation of conditions for successful socialization of minors, creation of their readiness for self-development, self-determination and responsible attitude to their life; strengthening of the family institution; protection of the rights of minors; creation of conditions for creation of worthy life perspective; defines the main directions of development of the system of prevention of neglect and juvenile delinquency; provides for improvement of normative-legal regulation, development of effective model of the system of prevention of delinquency and juvenile delinquency, development of human resource system (“Concept for the development of the system for the prevention of child neglect and juvenile delinquency for the period from 2017 to 2020”). The Federal Target Programme “Russia without orphans” for years 2013-2020 (2012) identifies four main subprogrammes: “Prevention of family disadvantage and social orphanhood”, “Orphans”, “Family forms of the arrangement of life of orphans”, “Prevention of deviant behavior of orphans”.

This programme differs from previous federal target programmes because it considers orphans and children without parental care as the main target group, this programme has its systematic approach to helping with family disadvantage and improving the situation of this category of children, and it is focused on a set of measures: early prevention of child abandonment; cultivation of traditional family values; orientation towards creating and supporting big families, including adopted children in families with many children, expanding family forms of placement for orphans and children left without parental care and ensuring their variability; creating the most optimal conditions for raising children in Russia, both biological and substitute families; encouraging Russian adoption and other forms of family placement for children in families of Russian citizens; minimizing the practice of adoption Russian children by foreign citizens living abroad; deinstitutionalization and downsizing of children’s orphanages and their conversion into modern centres with all needed human resources and material, technical, educational and methodological facilities, so that these centres would be training and professional support centres for foster and other substitute families, and as well as for rehabilitation, social adaptation and professional guidance centres for orphans and children left without parental care; redistribution of budget funds: from the financing of State orphanages to the full support of families which took orphans and children without parental care (Federal Target Programme “Russia without orphans” for years 2013-2020).

In the 1990s, on the background of a severe political crisis, the entire Soviet system was criticized, and problems of a social and economic nature were most affected by the most vulnerable categories of the population (children, disabled people, senior citizen). During these years, publications appeared that criticized the Soviet system of orphanages and boarding schools. In them, boarding schools were presented as large inefficient complexes with no conditions for preparing pupils for adult life in the time of market economy and decommunization of society. Now it is necessary to restore the attitude to the Soviet period of work of boarding schools, and also to reveal in a heritage of teachers of boarding pedagogy the ideas significant for the present.

At present, as in the Soviet period, development of the personality of orphans and children left without parental care is organized in special boarding schools as educational and training process as well as their preparation for further independent life. In carrying out this training, teachers' teams turn to the heritage of teachers of the past. On this basis, the demand for creative, substantial and methodical potential of the Soviet education; the analysis of theoretical developments and applied methods of the process of socialization of the child are of great importance.

That's why for example Boguslavsky (2016) writes: "...the potential of historical and pedagogical knowledge is actualized, its demand for modern Russian education is growing and the impact on educational policy is increasing... there is a natural actualization of all retrospective national-patriotic problems, ideological-theoretical and scientific potential of Soviet pedagogy..." (p. 6).

Purpose and objectives of the study

The aim of the study is to present in a holistic form, based on the materials of residential institutions for orphans in the late XX - early XXI century in the context of the ideas of Kondratenkov (1921-1992), the practical implementation of the process of preparing orphans and children left without parental care to independent life in society.

Literature review

We have analyzed a number of works representing an interweaving of the main pedagogical concepts of the middle XX century (collective, labor activity, personality) and the beginning of the XXI century (individual, communication, children's community). This combination of concepts is reflected in scientific works of Antonova (2004), E. Logacheva (2013), Chepuryskin (2004). We also consider the main ideas of Alexander Kondratenkov, which formed the basis of educational institutions for orphans in the modern time, which are set out in the following works of the teacher: The team is responsible for everyone (Kondratenkov, 1967); Do not forget about your duty (Kondratenkov, 1973); To study in the fullest extent of power (Kondratenkov, 1966 a). № 6; To become independent (Kondratenkov, 1966 b). № 3; Work and Talent of a Teacher. Meetings. Facts. Thoughts (Kondratenkov, 1985); Pedagogy in Pictures of Real Life (Kondratenkov, 1993).

Methodology

The most important methods of research were general theoretic methods (analysis, synthesis, actualization, systematization), historical and pedagogical methods (revealing of the basic conditions of personality's formation of an orphanage child in boarding institutions in the end of XX - beginning of XXI centuries in the context of Kondratenkov's ideas).

Results

In the 1960s, boarding schools were opened in Russia for orphans and children left without parental care. These educational institutions played a major role in the system of boarding schools. Boarding schools were characterized by the creation of favourable conditions for the upbringing and socialization of orphans, the diversity of methods, forms and means aimed at the comprehensive harmonious development of the personality of the pupils, and the development of their skills and abilities necessary for their further independent life in society.

One of the biggest boarding schools in the country was the Safonovo boarding school in the Smolensk region. This educational institution was opened in March 1960. The structure of the boarding school included nursery, kindergarten and school. The pedagogical staff of the Safonovo boarding school was the first in the USSR which began to implement in practice the task of raising children from early, pre-school education to secondary education.

Kondratenkov (1921-1992) headed the boarding school, later he became Corresponding Member of the USSR Academy of Sciences, Honored Teacher of the RSFSR school. For many years he taught at a rural school, carefully and thoughtfully engaged in the education of children and youth. From 1951 to 1956 Kondratenkov worked as director of Kobylkinskaya secondary school of Hislavichi district in Smolensk region, then he was appointed as director of Safonovo boarding school.

In Kondratenkov's personal characteristic stands that "as a school director, he is characterized by a constant interest in the achievements of pedagogical science and practice ... a sense of the new, the search for ways and means of improving the effectiveness of classes with children and teenager, the ability to organize teachers and pupils to achieve the goal" (Kondratenkov's personal characteristic, p. 2). The teacher began his work in the boarding school by studying the existing experience of early childhood educators and preschool children, schools and boarding schools in the Smolensk region, Moscow, Kiev, Donetsk and other cities, with an analysis of special teaching literature.

The idea of all-round personal development is also reflected in the organization of educational work with the pupils of Safonovo boarding school. For realization of this idea the perspective planning (for five-six years) of arrangement of the pedagogical staff in boarding school was developed, giving the chance to the teacher of primary classes in advance to know, what concrete group of preschool children will come in his first class. Significant forms of cooperation between educators and teachers were the establishment and maintenance of constant communication for a number of years between primary school teachers and the teachers of the pre-school department, whose pupils would eventually become pupils of this teacher. Such interaction allowed each teacher to study each child in detail and to have the fullest possible idea of the content, forms and methods of all educational work with children prior to the school stage of study and upbringing (Kondratenkov, 1985).

Preparing for classes with children, teachers of the Safonovo boarding school also developed the idea of naturalness. Teachers and educators analyzed the emerging system of educational and extracurricular activities, found out how it corresponds to the age and individual characteristics of children, striving to ensure that the whole lesson - from the first to the last minute - was filled with interesting work. Moreover, the organization of such work was not only designed for the whole class in general, but also took into account the individual characteristics of each student, it means the method

of differentiating tasks for the independent work of pupils in the lessons (in combination with front forms) was actively used (Kondratenkov, 1966).

In carrying out the process of labour education, the pedagogical staff of the boarding school ensured that any work performed by pupils and its results would be assessed by the team of pupils and the public; pupils had a clear understanding of the importance of the work performed, had prior knowledge of how to work, were able to use the instruments and were obliged to observe the requirements of occupational health.

The main types of the pupils' work included work of the older children of the preschool department on the daily care of their sleeping place, work on the land, daily household and household work of the pupils 1st-2nd grades, work on the improvement of the children's town (landscaping, care of trees and bushes, floriculture, etc.), repairing of furniture and household equipment, participation in duties, patronage, work in the greenhouse, on the farm, in educational and production facilities, in the state farm.

As for moral education, all educational work with children, teenager and older pupils in the Safonovo boarding school was based on the principles of the Moral Code of a New Person. In addition to explaining statements of the Code, systematic exercises have been conducted to develop and consolidate the skills of high moral behaviour. The plans of the group's educators and the school plan of mass events provided for work on teaching pupils to understand what should be the moral image of a Soviet person, on teaching every pupil the features of Soviet patriotism and proletarian internationalism, honest attitude to work and public property, collectivity, a sense of duty, honor and humanism.

All educators and class teachers ensured that any act of a pupil and, above all, the attitude of pupils to their teaching, work, to the rules of the dormitory, to friends and parents received timely and correct assessment in the team. In addition, the ties between the pupils' primary teams and the employees of production enterprises and state farms were strengthened. It was considered necessary that each class had its own collective chief - a workshop, a brigade, a link in the enterprise or state farm (Kondratenkov, 1965).

The creation of the personality of an orphan child was also carried out in the process of aesthetic education. Thus, senior educators periodically updated the art gallery and conducted work to acquaintance pupils with works of art (excursions, essays, etc.). Months of acquaintance with works of literature and art were also held in the school. Artists, writers and composers were periodically invited to the boarding school to meet with the pupils. Pupils prepared concerts for such meetings.

Boarding school provided a successful solution to a number of tasks defined by the physical education system. The complex of events for physical education, carried out during a day, promoted comprehensive development of pupils' abilities, strengthening of their health, gave them knowledge in the field of physical culture and sports and prepared them for work. The school was notable for its wide coverage of pupils in various forms of physical education. A good material base of the boarding school provided year-round trainings in various sports. The main activities of physical education were "morning gymnastics and games; hours of gymnastics and active games; rhythmic in music education, sports entertainment and competitions; walks" (Belov, 1963).

Kondratenkov paid great attention to the role of the family in the creation of the personality of an orphan child. In the 1970s, his works on the interaction between family and school for the successful development of the child's personality, family education are published ("Do not forget about your duty" and "Notes of the school director").

In them, Kondratenkov states how important the connection with the parents is for the child. The loss of this connection leads to irreversible consequences, only together with the family the boarding school can find a solution to many problems in the education of orphans and achieve success. Kondratenkov was fatherly strict and fair. That's why he was respected by pupils and colleagues. In the archive of the Safonovo boarding school we found documents containing memoirs of the teachers of the boarding school in Kondratenkov's time: "we never allowed ourselves to be late for the lesson, as for an hour we had to go to the dormitory to talk to the child face to face" (Report on the status of educational work in a boarding school (1962-63), p. 6).

Therefore, the key ideas expressed in the specific pedagogical approaches of Kondratenkov, director of the largest Safonovo boarding school in the USSR, an innovator in the field of education, aimed at the socialization of orphans, were the connection of study with work; comprehensive harmonious development of the pupils' personality; naturalness; gradualness, consistency and certainty (specificity) in the organization of work with the pupils of different ages; creation of a family moral environment, safety and security, orientation on advanced technologies that were relevant to a particular historical period. Kondratenkov's ideas are also reflected in the post-Soviet period in the organization of educational work of boarding schools in Russia and abroad. As an example, we will consider the work experience of boarding schools in Russia and abroad.

At the end of XX - beginning of XXI century 347 family-type orphanages were opened in Russia, 3,5 thousand orphans were brought up in them. In 1996, a family-type children's home "Gnezdysk" ("Nest") was opened in Smolensk, where children live in "apartments" of one mixed-age family. If the children are related by blood, they are not divided into different orphanages. In addition, an educator is attached to each child as a tutor. The family environment prevails in the orphanage. Family meals, care for each other, etc. are practiced here as forms of education. All children study in a regular general education school.

Kondratenkov's ideas are also reflected in the organization of educational work in the Pochinok Special (Correctional) Boarding School in the Smolensk region, headed by the follower of Kondratenkov's ideas, PhD in Pedagogy, honored teacher of Russia Igor Chepuryskin. Based on the theoretical and methodological and practice-oriented attitudes formulated in the 60s by Kondratenkov director Chepuryskin and his colleagues determine the priority psychological, pedagogical and medical-social support for orphans, children without parental care, disabled children, children from dysfunctional families and families with one parent. They are working to lay the foundations for the development and corrective interaction between an adult and a child with a view to developing a mechanism for compensating by every child. Pedagogical meetings are held in the forms of a business simulation game "New technologies in educational work"; a productive game "Conflict and stressful situations in relation between a child and an adult" with self-assessment of communicative qualities; an open microphone "Psychological and pedagogical culture as the main factor of teachers' skill"; brainstorming "Development of a model of developing and dynamic school" (Chepuryskin, 2004).

As for the education of children, in addition to the basic subjects, special classes are held, such as “correction in play”, “choice of profession”, “ethics and psychology of family life”, “chemistry in the household” and “physics in the household”. In addition, teachers in grades 3 to 8 have extra-curricular activities on the basic concepts of economics. The purpose of these classes is to provide the child with a system of basic economic knowledge in a way that they can understand. Lessons are held in a non-traditional form through games, practical tasks, solving problem situations. Traditional extra-curricular rhetorical classes are successfully held, allowing to master communication skills and to develop a general culture of pupils’ speech. In order to broaden the horizons, develop and correct speech, and socialize the personality, each class has optional activities. The boarding school offers the option of obtaining professional skills in equipped workshops for the professions of carpenter, plumber, seamstress. At the carpentry workshop pupils acquire woodworking skills necessary for their daily lives. In the plumber workshop children learn to read drawings, plan the work, make markings, perform manual, machine and heat treatment. Personal qualities such as diligence, accuracy, sense of responsibility are formed in such workshops. In the shoe shop, students acquire knowledge, skills and abilities in repairing and sewing shoes. In grades 1-3, manual labour lessons are taught, while in grade 4, manual labour lessons are taught as propaedeuticals to develop new skills and behaviours characteristic of a professional workshop. In sewing workshops girls learn to perform various types of decorative stitches, sweep the hinges. In these workshops girls have the opportunity to get all the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities of sewing. In addition to the program material, girls learn to embroider in satin-stitch, to stitch cross, richelieu, to sew applications, to make weave products, macrame techniques and other types of needlework. At the end of the school year, girls of 4-8 grades show their skills at the contest “Fashion and Time”, which has already become traditional. Clothes sewn with their own hands are shown by the students. Children have various competitions. Within the framework of the competition exhibitions of works made in workshops are held. Boys usually take part in the competition programme “City of Masters”.

The boarding school has a room for social and household orientation. The aim of the classes in this room is practical preparation of children for independent life and work, formation of skills that promote social and household adaptation, integration into society, development of personal qualities. Lessons are held using the latest household appliances (toaster, fryers, electric grinders, juicers, kitchen combine), which students learn to use in the household. The study of topics provides an opportunity to form and improve the necessary skills of household management, self-service. Pupils learn such topics as personal hygiene, food serving, plant care (seasonal work on the land, indoor plants and care for them), family, home.

The team of teachers creates all the necessary conditions for normal life activities of children, recognizes the right of every student to a standard of living necessary for their adequate physical and social development. Training courses for teachers are regularly held in the boarding school on the subject of “Psychological and pedagogical rehabilitation of abnormal children in correctional boarding schools”, followed by a scientific and practical conference on “Social adaptation and psychological, medical and pedagogical rehabilitation of children in special correctional boarding schools”.

It is also necessary to note new forms of work in boarding school such as the literary and introductory program “National Symbols”, “Star hour”, “My rights and obligations”, “Politeness”. These forms of work make it possible to raise

children's communicative qualities, to introduce them with real life standards, to build relationships, to develop a sense of responsibility, initiative and independence.

Thus, the idea of creating a family environment, security, orientation to those technologies that are relevant and significant for a particular historical period prevails in these boarding schools. If in the 60s of the XX century it was the idea of polytechnism, nowadays it is the idea of digitalization. The idea of creating a family environment is also reflected in the experience of foreign educational institutions for orphans and children left without parental care. Now we consider in more detail the implementation of this idea on the example of specific residential institutions.

The family forms of placement of orphaned children have been leading in Sweden, the Netherlands and Belgium since the 1990s. Thus, Antonova (2004) in her book "Protection of Childhood from Risks in Foreign Education" notes: "the system of care of orphans in Sweden has passed in the second half of XX century two stages: 40s - 80s - closure of orphanages, 90s - introduction of the family into the category of childcare institutions. The work on closing orphanages was carried out by the institution "Barniun Sko" (Stockholm), which became an ideological center for the development of future social care for children, both in Sweden and other Scandinavian countries. Children were accommodated in families and the organization worked with them at home instead of in an orphanage. The strategy was not only to accommodate the child in the centre of attention, but also to confront processes that excluded the family from society. The activities of the staff were moved to the children's homes and microenvironment" (Antonova, 2004, p. 22).

Temporary orphanages in Sweden brought up children who had a bad relationship with their parents, from a few weeks to 12 years. If the parents changed their attitude, the child would return home after eight weeks, and for those who continued to stay in the institution, conditions would be created close to home. These are joint evenings, watching TV programs, organizing games and holidays. Each pupil had his own room, he could be visited by friends and classmates. The children attended regular schools and kindergartens. If after six months it was not possible to establish relations with relatives, the upbringing of the child was temporarily entrusted to another family with which the contract for one year was concluded. During the year, biological parents could meet with their children in new families.

In the Netherlands, day care was used as a form of social protection. The assistance programme was fully state-funded and provided work for teenagers and young people in the age between 12 and 21 years who had dropped out of school and had no job or social support. The programme was implemented at youth social assistance centres. Teenagers and young people worked in small groups of ten, they were provided with the opportunity to gain positive experience of communication, change their attitude to themselves and develop social skills.

An example of family-type boarding school is the SOS Children's Village, which was first established in Austria, where the idea of creating institutions for children without parents, replacing the functions of parents, was born. As practice has shown, Children's Villages "SOS Kinderdorf" are a successful initiative here. In 1949, Dr. G. Gmeiner built the first orphanage in Imst. The children lived in a family with the children of different sex and age. The mother-educator was engaged in cooking, laundry and cleaning. The house was the centre of the Gmeiner's model and was part of the children's village. The idea of Gmeiner was supported by teachers and the public (Logacheva, 2013). There are six SOS

Children's Villages in Russia. For example, one of them is located in the village of Tomilino, Lyuberetsky district of Moscow region.

Logacheva (2013) in the article "Children's Villages: SOS-Moms and Home Comfort for Orphans" writes: "If there weren't a signboard at the gate, nobody would have distinguished the children's orphanage in Tomilino from the usual cottage village. There are 11 spacious brick houses, children's playgrounds, paved paths. Each cottage has a large family headed with an SOS-mother. Children here live in their rooms, can go to an ordinary village school, although there is also their own school on the territory. And they can also do what many other children from boarding schools are unable to do: help their mother around the house, shop on their own, go somewhere outside the institution" (Logacheva, 2013, p. 5).

Orphans from Moscow and other cities of Russia get into Tomilino. At present 47 children live in a children's village in Tomilino: "The orphanage is two thirds full. The children from the children's village are ordinary children who have found themselves in a difficult life situation. Some of them have lost their parents, others are social orphans, it means the mother or father has been deprived of parental rights. Priority is given to brothers and sisters from large families. At adoption they can be separated, can go to different boarding schools, and in children's villages they have all the conditions to live together. The children have life skills. They know how to go to the shop, go to school, and use public transport. And the children leave this village more prepared for the life than in any other boarding school" (Logacheva, 2013, p. 6).

A form of assistance to children, such as temporary orphanage, should also be considered. The first temporary social orphanage "House of Mercy" was opened in St. Petersburg in the 1990s. The main principle in the educational work of the orphanage's educators was to attract children to work.

This Russian experience in creating temporary orphanages is based on the experience of creating temporary children's orphanage in the United States. As Antonova (2004) notes: "In the United States, an important place in the system of children's institutions is occupied by a fairly wide network of boarding schools for orphans and abandoned children. There are also orphanages for children and teenagers who have experienced emotional breakdown. These institutions work as hospitals and serve as rehabilitation centres for children from dysfunctional families, teenagers who have run away from home or who have committed minor offences. Each center is designed for only 8-10 children. There are more than 200 of them across the country. Educators in these centers are able to work professionally individually with each child and with the group, to relieve stress experienced by the child, and act as advisers. The U.S. government's Adoption Assistance Act and the Child Care Act address children's need for continuity and stability. A child's stay in an institution is considered a temporary measure; accommodation of children outside their home is allowed for a maximum of 18 months. At the end of the period, a decision must be made which family is responsible for raising the child. If the biological family has been unable to rehabilitate itself, it is recommended to accommodate the child in a new family. At the same time, the children were placed close to home so that the biological parents could participate in the life of the children more often. The special children's institution, where children from the age of 12 live and grow up, is as close to the family type as possible: several dozens of children live there, so that the educators can professionally carry out an individual approach and show constant care for every child" (Antonova, 2004, p. 25).

In addition, the form of assistance to children in difficult situations, such as boarding houses and social protection centres, should also be considered. In St. Petersburg, for example, the Government centre for the social protection of street children “Vospitatelny dom” (“Educational Home”) is working. It works not only with children, but also with their parents. Currently, there are about 12 rehabilitation departments. Every department has different focus areas: children’s health, cultural education, protection of their rights and interests, and social support for foster families. For 20 years almost 10000 children have passed through this institution, and this is 10000 children’s lives saved! In addition, for 20 years now, “Vospitatelny dom” is the main methodological center of the city, where the staff is looking for new forms of work with children and families.

This Russian experience is based on the activities of special institutions in Belgium and Vietnam aimed at providing social and educational support to families and children. The Institute “Our Children” in Belgium is undoubtedly one of the institutions providing social and pedagogical assistance to children who have found themselves outside the family. It is made up a network of individual institutions with a capacity for 15-20 people, located in small towns and villages. Children of the same sex and of the same or different age are living in different institutions. Each child has its own room, which is furnished to his or her own taste. Children enjoy freedom of movement, take part in cooking and cleaning the room. Children spend their free time at their own discretion. Psychological, medical and social centres with a counselling function are also popular in Belgium. These centres have been established in major cities to provide support to educational institutions, children and their families. In Vietnam there are also family-type social protection centres. Residents of these centres are divided into small groups or families, each with a mother and 6-8 siblings of different age. However, such institutions are unable to replace for children their families, and the children continue to experience maternal deprivation. In the most cases, these centres are isolated from the surrounding community because children have limited access outside the centre.

In St. Petersburg Christian Maiden’s Boarding Home “Enfilia” with an orphanage “Little Mom” live underage mothers who find themselves in a difficult life situation. The orphanage works in a mode of a round-the-clock stationary for 15 places. It also provides social patronage for up to six months. The institution provides educational, psychological and medical assistance to young mothers with children who find themselves without budget for living and have lost the care of their relatives and friends.

Girls attend classes at the “Young Mother’s School” where they have conversations, practical exercises, open events, where they learn basics of housekeeping and hygiene skills. There are also “creative workshops” where they learn handicrafts.

In our opinion, such social and pedagogical rehabilitation contributes to the improvement of communication skills of the girls. They begin to show independence in solving social and domestic problems, they have an increased sense of responsibility for the child, reduced anxiety, an active life position and confidence in their abilities.

Specialists do a lot for girls and their children during their stay in the orphanage, but the most important test begins after the independent life starts, when there are no people who are ready to help at any time.

Discussions

What are the methods, forms and means of labour, physical, moral and aesthetic education aimed at preparing children for further life in society in the conditions of modern boarding schools? What ideas of soviet pedagogy may be relevant to the work of modern boarding schools for orphans and children without parental care? What is the continuity in the activity of boarding schools teachers in different historical periods?

Conclusion

Summing up, we can conclude that the ideas of one of the founders of boarding pedagogy Kondratenkov remain relevant and are reflected in the educational work of modern boarding schools for orphans and children left without parental care. The most significant of them are creation of family moral environment, safety, orientation on the advanced technologies which are significant for the concrete historical period (for 60th years of XX century it is the idea of polytechnism, for the present it is the idea of digitalization).

Thus, the pupils are prepared for further independent life in modern boarding schools through family education, in the form of family meals and care for each other; children's involvement in labour, cultural education, training in the basics of household management and hygiene skills. Characteristic features of boarding schools also include the protection of the rights and interests of their inmates, the provision of pedagogical, psychological and medical assistance, social and legal protection, innovative technologies for the upbringing and socialization of children, the introduction of new methods of educational work aimed at creation the personality of the children and the publication of new methodological materials necessary for work with orphans and children left without parental care.

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